

MECHANISMS OF REHABILITATION AND TRAINING OF PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7636219>

ELSEVIER

Received: 11-02-2023
Accepted: 12-02-2023
Published: 22-02-2023

Abstract: Implementation of the main directions of rehabilitation and health of the disabled implies the use of technical means of rehabilitation of the disabled, creation of necessary conditions for the unhindered access of the disabled to social, engineering and transport infrastructure facilities. The article also provides information on rehabilitation of disabled people and their families, rehabilitation of disabled people.

Keywords: social work, rehabilitation, technical means, rehabilitation, infrastructure, mechanism of adjustment, international standards.

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, more than 700,000 people with disabilities live in Uzbekistan, including more than 100,000 children with disabilities under the age of 16. Adoption of the Law on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, which stipulates the use of the term "disabled person" instead of "disabled person" in accordance with the international standards and requirements of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, served to express the rights and interests of representatives of the above category of our country. In the speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the 46th session of the UN Human Rights Council, he proposed to establish a Regional Council on the issues of full realization of the abilities of persons with disabilities. This proposal can be noted as a high-quality view of the activities aimed at the protection of persons with disabilities in our republic.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The World Health Organization estimates that more than one billion people, or 15% of the world's population, have some form of disability, and only 5% of these forms of disability are congenital. According to the United Nations Development Program (UNDP), 80% of people with disabilities live in developing countries. The World Bank estimates that 20 percent of the world's poorest people are people with disabilities.

People with disabilities are the largest minority in the world, but unlike other minority groups, this group always has open membership: any of us can become a

member of this group at any time due to accident, illness or aging. . Thus, disability is a part of human life. In most cases, disability is believed to be caused by social, economic or political factors, accidents or armed conflicts. Now there are more factors that lead to ill health, particularly environmental pollution, HIV/AIDS and drug addiction. Disability is also a development problem because it is linked to poverty: disability can increase the risk of poverty, and poverty can increase the risk of disability. Up to 50% of disability cases are preventable and directly related to poverty.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Due to the fact that disabled people have limited physical, intellectual and other health-related opportunities, they are considered members of society who need to organize special processes and social technologies for their full life. Technologies of social work with persons with disabilities offer a sequence of actions based on the professional skills of a social worker, activation of personal resources of a person with disabilities, and individual techniques aimed at getting out of a difficult life situation. The result of the application of social work technologies is the complete or partial recovery of the disabled person in his family, social and professional activities.

Technologies for social work with people with disabilities differ dramatically in content. We name the most important ones that are often used in the practical work of a social worker: social rehabilitation technology, social adaptation, social therapy, social diagnostics, etc.

Social rehabilitation of persons with disabilities as a technology includes measures aimed at restoring the ability of a disabled person to live in a social environment. It consists of socio-ecological orientation, social adaptation, socio-psychological, socio-pedagogical and socio-cultural rehabilitation.

The technology of social adaptation of a person with a disability is aimed at aligning his individual and group behavior with the current system of norms and values.

Among the general technologies of social work with persons with disabilities, the technology of social therapy is of special importance. It is a combination of techniques and techniques of social, visual, musical creativity that ensures the inclusion of a person with a disability in the environment. Active participation of a person with a disability in various creative activities allows him to develop or compensate his abilities, equalize or increase his social status.

CONCLUSION

Thus, the main criteria for the development of social skills of a disabled person are the following categories of life:

- self-care (the ability to independently satisfy a person's physiological needs, cook, perform daily tasks at home, personal hygiene, plan a daily routine);
- independent action;
- orientation (adequate perception of the environment, assessment of the situation, ability to determine time and place);
- communication (the ability to establish communication between people by receiving, processing and transmitting information);

Determining the social skills of a disabled person, determining the level of their formation is carried out using social diagnostic methods: observation, questionnaires, interviews, study of living conditions, analysis of documents.

LIST OF REFERENCES:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy Majlisi Senatining yettinchi yalpi majlisi to'g'risidagi AXBOROT <http://isrs.uz/oz/ozbekiston-yangiliklari/informacia-osedmom-plenarnom-zasedanii-senata-olij-mazlisa-respubliki-uzbekistan> (15.05.2021)
2. Prezident Shavkat Mirziyoevning BMT Inson huquqlari bo'yicha kengashining 46-sessiyasidagi nutqi <https://iiv.uz/uz/news/prezident-shavkat-mirziyoevning-bmt-inson-huquqlari-boyicha-kengashining-46-sessiyasidagi-nutqi> (15.05.2021)
3. Организация Объединенных Наций, 2008, «Координация вопросов инвалидности в повестке дня развития (E/CN.5/2008/6)»: www.un.org/disabilities/documents/reports/e-cn5-2008-6.doc
4. ООН, 2006, «Некоторые факты об инвалидах», Международная конвенция о правах инвалидов: www.un.org/disabilities/convention/pdfs/factsheet.pdf
5. ВОЗ, «Всемирный доклад об инвалидности»
6. Аъзамова, З., & Турсуналиева, Э. (2022). РОЛЬ И СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЕ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ПЕНСИОННОЙ СИСТЕМЫ В СИСТЕМЕ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ЗАЩИТЫ. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(10), 740-745.
7. Azamova, Z., & Tursunaliyeva, E. (2022). Reintegration of Persons Returning from Labor Migration and Their Employment. *Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 13, 122-126.
8. Tursunaliyeva, E., & Azamova, Z. (2022). Reintegration of Persons Returning from Labor Migration and Ensuring Their Employment. *Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities*, 11, 171-175.

9. Zarnigorxon A'Zamova, Kamola Sharipova, & E'Zozaxon Tursunaliyeva (2022). YETIM VA OTA-ONA QARAMOG'IDAN MAHRUM BO'LGAN BOLALARNI MAKTABLARDA SIFATLI TA'LIM VA TARBIYA OLISHDAGI MUAMMOLARI. *Research Focus*, 1 (2), 301-306.